

1 **Application of a novel approach to modelling the supercritical**

2 **extraction kinetics of oil from two sets of chia seeds**

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27 **Abstract**

28 The kinetics of the supercritical fluid extraction of edible (ECS) and discarded (DCS) chia seeds
29 was studied and modelled for the first time. The total oil was removed at 45 MPa and 60 °C after
30 240 min. The extraction kinetics was simulated using a dynamic model in gPROMS
31 ModelBuilder environment and the kinetic parameters estimated. Triolein was chosen as a model
32 compound of the chia oil. The agreement between the experimental yields and those calculated
33 by the model was good with deviations in the range (1.2-6.6) %, except at 25 MPa and 60 °C
34 (AARD = 9.5%).

35

36 **Keywords:** Chia seed oil; supercritical CO₂ extraction; polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA); α -
37 linolenic acid (ALA); extraction kinetics; mathematical modelling.

38

39 **1. Introduction**

40 At present, there is a constant search of promising and inexpensive vegetal materials as a source
41 of polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFAs). Chia (*Salvia hispanica* L.), a plant indigenous to
42 Guatemala and Mexico, which belongs to the Lamiaceae family, is attracting a great attention,
43 especially the seeds. Chia seeds are being studied as a source of food ingredients, such as proteins
44 and dietary fiber [1-3], but they mainly stand out for their high oil content (20-35 mass %). Chia
45 seed oil contains significant amounts of PUFAs, mainly the omega-3 α -linolenic acid (ALA) (60-
46 65% of total fatty acids) [4], which role in the prevention of cardiovascular, nervous system and
47 inflammatory diseases has been thoroughly described [5,6].

48 Thus far, different solvents (ethyl acetate, acetone, propane, petroleum ether and hexane) and
49 extraction techniques (cold and hot pressing, Soxhlet, Ultrasound-Assisted Extraction and
50 Pressurized Liquid Extraction) have been applied to obtain chia seed oil [7-11]. A viable and eco-
51 friendly alternative to the use of organic toxic solvents is the extraction with supercritical CO₂
52 (scCO₂), which is non-toxic, non-flammable, non-mutagenic and carcinogenic and is abundant
53 and inexpensive. Moreover, due to the possibility of working at low temperatures and in the
54 absence of oxygen, supercritical extraction with scCO₂ (SCE) prevents or minimizes the

55 degradation of bioactive compounds and allows obtainment of solvent-free products [12]. New
56 developments regarding the application of this advanced technique to obtain oils were reported
57 recently in the literature. For example, Wei et al. [13] employed ultrasound-assisted supercritical
58 carbon dioxide extraction (scCO₂) for removing oleanolic acid (OA) and ursolic acid (UA) from
59 *Hedyotis corymbosa*. The experimental solubility data, called by the authors fictitious, were read
60 from the initial slope of the curve of the extraction yield versus the amount of scCO₂ used, and
61 were modelled applying several semi-empirical density-based models. Moon et al. [14] studied
62 the scCO₂ extraction, with and without co-solvent (ethanol) of the essential oil from *Asiasarum*
63 *heterotropoides* and the results obtained were compared with conventional extraction. In another
64 study [15], turmeric (*Curcuma longa* L.) was extracted with scCO₂ and turmerones were
65 concentrated using semi-preparative supercritical chromatography. Supercritical fluid extraction
66 with a co-solvent was also applied to extract oil from rice bran with the aim to promote the
67 valorization of this abundant feedstock [16]. Concerning SCE of chia seed oil, as far as we are
68 aware, only a few studies have been carried out till present [17-20]. In those, the concentration of
69 ALA achieved in the extracted oil was approximately (60-65) %, hence SCE process allowed
70 obtaining healthy and high-quality oils regardless of the operational parameters applied.

71 It is known that kinetic data are essential for the realization of a feasible industrial process.
72 However, despite the aforementioned and the possibilities to realize a viable industrial process,
73 kinetic data are not only scarce and superficial, but also, as far as we are aware, there are no
74 attempts related to the modelling of SCE of oil from chia seeds reported in the literature till
75 present. Accordingly, two were the objectives of this work: *i*) to provide new data on the scCO₂
76 extraction of chia oil and *ii*) to apply a novel approach to the extraction kinetics modelling,
77 advocated originally by Sovová and Stateva [21]. This approach reflects the interaction between
78 kinetics and phase equilibria (solubility) and applies a reliable and versatile modeling framework
79 to estimate the solubility of the oil in the supercritical fluid, as discussed in **some details** in Section
80 2.5.

81 To achieve the objectives of our work, edible chia seeds (ECS), and discarded seeds (DCS) were
82 studied. Particularly for the latter, the present investigation can be of considerable interest as it

83 will provide information on how to intensify further their valorization and industrial applications.
84 So far, the studies reported in the literature have been carried out by using ECS. Chia seeds
85 employed in the present study were subjected to a selection process in which the seeds were
86 classified in different qualities mainly based on their weight, intactness, color, visual aspect and
87 size. Thus, DCS consist of damaged, partially broken and/or smaller-size and lower-weight seeds
88 that are usually discarded during post-harvest handling and finally intended to animal feeding.
89 Their price, as a consequence of the market surplus of this product, is considerably lower than
90 that of ECS. Even though they are an underutilized raw material, DCS possess a noteworthy
91 amount of oil and may constitute a viable alternative source for obtaining highly polyunsaturated
92 chia seed oils to be used in human health care formulations.

93

94 **2. Materials and methods**

95 **2.1 Sample preparation**

96 The two different sets of chia seeds (*Salvia hispanica* L.) originating from Mexico were purchased
97 from a local supplier (Primaria). The oil content for each set of seeds (28.3% and 19.9% mass for
98 ECS and DCS, respectively) was determined by pressurized liquid extraction by using a 2:1
99 chloroform:methanol mixture at 60 °C and 10 min of extraction time [22]. These results are in
100 agreement with the values provided by the supplier for each set (25.2% and 20.6%, respectively).

101 In what follows we will use the oil content values obtained by us for each set of seeds.

102 The seeds were ground in a knife mill cooled by liquid nitrogen. Ground seeds were sieved using
103 mesh sizes of 0.250 and 0.500 mm Ø (CISA Cedaceria Industrial S.L. Barcelona, Spain). An
104 average particle diameter (d_p) of 0.370 mm was obtained, using Eq. (1):

$$d_p = \frac{M_t}{\sum_{i=1}^j \frac{m_i}{d_{pi}}} \quad (1)$$

105 where M_t is the total mass of milled seeds, m_i - the mass of the particles kept below mesh size
106 d_{pi} and j - the number of mesh sizes.

107 Samples obtained were stored at -20 °C until their use.

108

109 **2.2 Chemicals**

110 Dichloromethane, hexane, methanol, acetonitrile, dimethylformamide (HPLC grade) and sulfuric
111 acid (98% purity) were purchased from Labscan (Dublin, Ireland). Sodium carbonate, sea sand
112 and sodium sulfate anhydrous were supplied by Panreac (Barcelona, Spain). Sodium methoxide
113 (95% purity) was supplied by Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, MO, USA). Butterfat BCR-164 (EU
114 Commissions; Brussels, Belgium) was supplied by Fedelco Inc. (Madrid, Spain). CO₂ (99.99%
115 purity) was supplied by Carbueros Metálicos (Madrid, Spain).

116

117 **2.3 Supercritical CO₂ extraction**

118 The SCEs were performed in a pilot-plant supercritical fluid extractor (model SF2000; Thar
119 Technology, Pittsburgh, PA, USA), equipped with a 273 cm³ cylinder extraction cell (18.8 cm
120 long and 4.3 cm internal diameter) and two separators (0.5 L capacity). A thorough description
121 of the equipment can be found in Villanueva-Bermejo et al. [23].

122 The SCEs from DCS were carried out at $p = (25 \text{ and } 45) \text{ MPa}$ and $T = (40 \text{ and } 60) \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The CO₂
123 flow rate and extraction times were, respectively, 40 g·min⁻¹ and 240 min for all the experiments
124 with this set of seeds. The extractions of ECS were performed at 45 MPa and 40 °C. Several CO₂
125 flow rates were studied, namely 27, 40 and 54 g·min⁻¹ (CO₂-to-seed ratio of 50, 74 and 100,
126 respectively). For all runs, the seeds mass used was 130 g, with an apparent density value of
127 $0.606 \pm 0.002 \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$. During the experiments the scCO₂ was recirculated. The entire extracts were
128 collected from the first separator (the mass of oil obtained from the second separator was
129 negligible) by depressurization at 5 MPa (system recirculation pressure). Oil samples were
130 dissolved in methylene chloride, treated with $\approx 1 \text{ g}$ of sodium sulfate anhydrous and filtered
131 through 0.45 μm filters. Finally, the samples were stored at -35 °C until analysis.

132

133 **2.4 Fatty acid profile**

134 The derivatization of fatty acids from chia oils was carried out following the method described
135 by Castro-Gómez et al. [24]. The analysis of fatty acid methyl esters (FAMES) were performed
136 in an Agilent chromatograph 6890N (Agilent Technologies Inc. Palo Alto, USA) equipped with

137 an MS detector (Agilent 5973N) and using CP-Sil 88 fused-silica capillary column (100 m × 0.25
138 mm ID × 0.2 μm. Chrompack, Middelburg, The Netherlands). The temperature program started
139 at 100 °C for 1 min and then the temperature increased by 7 °C·min⁻¹ up to 170 °C, followed by
140 an isothermal period of 55 min. Finally, temperature increased by 10° C·min⁻¹ up to 230 °C and
141 was held for 33 min. The injector temperature was 250 °C and helium was used as the carrier gas.
142 The analysis was carried out in split mode (split ratio 1:25) and the injection volume was 1 μL.
143 For the MS detector, the transfer line, source and quadrupole temperatures were 250 °C, 230 °C
144 and 150 °C, respectively. The mass spectrometer operated under electron impact mode (70 eV).
145 Eluting compounds were scanned in total ion current (TIC) mode in the mass range from 40 to
146 500 m·z⁻¹. The identification of target compounds was carried out by comparing their mass spectra
147 with those at the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) library (Gaithersburg,
148 MD, USA). The response factors were calculated using anhydrous milk fat (reference material
149 BCR-164). Tritridecanoic acid (C13:0) was used as an internal standard.

150

151 **2.5 Supercritical fluid extraction of chia oil – Modelling framework**

152 *Model description*

153 The model developed by Sovová and Stateva [21] for multicomponent systems was used in this
154 work. In brief, the approach reflects the interplay between solubility and kinetics. For that
155 purpose, a rigorous thermodynamic model is applied to estimate the solubility of the oil in the
156 supercritical fluid, and the resulting equations are incorporated into the dynamic model. Dynamic
157 simulation of the supercritical extraction process is then performed. The model considers that the
158 concentrations inside the extractor are homogeneous in the fluid and solid phases. Internal
159 diffusion is neglected based on the assumption that the extracts are located at the surface of the
160 solid particles, and hence easily available.

161 As the chia seeds used in our work were grounded to an average diameter of 0.370 mm, it was
162 considered that the resulting internal diffusion path for such small particles is short. Consequently,
163 the oil is easily available at the particle surface.

164 The model is described by the following set of equations:

$$\frac{dw}{dt} + \frac{w}{t_r} = \frac{k_f a_0}{\varepsilon} (w^+ - w) \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{dw_s}{dt} = -q' t_r \frac{k_f a_0}{\varepsilon} (w^+ - w) \quad (3)$$

$$w^+ = K w_s + \frac{w_s^b}{w_t^b + w_s^b} (w_{sat} - K w_s) \quad (4)$$

165 with the initial conditions:

$$w(0) = w_0 \quad (5)$$

$$w_s(0) = w_{s,0} \quad (6)$$

166 The yield, e (kg·kg⁻¹ solid), is defined by:

$$e = q' \int_0^t e dt \quad (4)$$

$$e(0) = 0 \quad (8)$$

167 where w is the oil concentration in the fluid phase inside the extractor (kg·kg⁻¹ CO₂), w_s - the oil
 168 concentration in the solid phase (kg·kg⁻¹ solid), t and t_r are the extraction and residence time (min),
 169 respectively, q' - the specific flow rate (kg CO₂·min⁻¹·kg⁻¹ solid), w^+ - the oil concentration at
 170 solid-fluid interface (kg·kg⁻¹ CO₂), ε - void fraction in the bed, $k_f a_0$ (min⁻¹) - the volumetric fluid
 171 phase mass transfer resistance, K (kg plant ·kg⁻¹ CO₂) - the partition coefficient, w_t (kg·kg⁻¹ CO₂)
 172 - the monolayer adsorption maximum content, w_{sat} (kg·kg⁻¹ CO₂) - the solubility of the free oil
 173 compound, and b is a coefficient that should be higher than one.

174 The model was deployed in gPROMS ModelBuilder [25], an equation-oriented modelling
 175 environment for dynamic (and steady-state) simulation that includes optimization and parameter
 176 estimation capabilities. It should be noted that the use of this kind of equation-oriented modelling
 177 and optimization software for supercritical CO₂ extraction has not been that much reported in the
 178 literature until now.

179 Some of the coefficients in the model are unknown and parameter estimation was performed to
 180 estimate these missing values. The simulated yield profiles were compared with the experimental
 181 data, and an objective function was used to minimize the error of the adjustment and obtain the
 182 parameter values that result in the best fit. Obtaining the solution of the resultant nonlinear

183 dynamic model may be challenging and may cause numerical convergence problems. Also,
184 locating the global optimum is not guaranteed. A shortage in experimental data may also
185 compromise the reliability of the results and the confidence interval associated with the solutions.
186 In this work, gPROMS ModelBuilder parameter estimation capabilities were used to obtain the
187 unknown parameters. gPROMS parameter estimation uses a maximum likelihood problem to
188 obtain the missing parameters. The interested reader can find more details on gPROMS
189 documentation [25].

190 To be able to relate the fitting accuracy achieved, a standard measure of deviation was used, the
191 absolute average relative deviation, AARD, defined by:

$$\text{AARD} = \frac{100}{N} \sum_{j=1}^N \frac{|e_i^{exp} - e_i^{est}|}{e_i^{exp}} \quad (9)$$

192 where N is the total number of experimentally measured points, e_i^{exp} and e_i^{est} are the i -th
193 experimental and estimated point, respectively.

194 ***Representation of the oil and correlation of its solubility in scCO₂***

195 The chia seed oil, as any other vegetable oil, is a very complex mixture of many compounds,
196 mainly triacylglycerols (TAGs) with minor amounts of other compounds such as free fatty acids,
197 mono- and diacylglycerols [26,27]. With the purpose of reducing the size of the kinetics
198 modelling task, a generally accepted approach is to exemplify the vegetable oil examined either
199 by one TAG only [28-30], or as a binary mixture of triolein and oleic acid [31]. Recently, there
200 were attempts to represent some vegetable oils as a mixture of several TAGs, with a varied success
201 – from a failure in the prediction of the phase equilibrium of the multicomponent mixture
202 examined [32] to an acceptable quantitative and qualitative representation of the kinetic curves
203 measured [33].

204 In the case of chia seed oil, our analyses show that linolenic acid is the fatty acid with the highest
205 content followed by linoleic acid. Hence, the TAGs trilinolenin and trilinolein are the main lipid
206 representatives in the oil.

207 To simulate the extraction kinetics of oil from the chia seeds, the phase behavior of the system
208 (oil and scCO₂) should be modeled, which requires an appropriate thermodynamic model by

209 which the solubility of the oil in the scCO₂ will be calculated. Then, following the algorithm
210 advocated in Sovova and Stateva [21], a second order polynomial function will be fitted to the
211 solubility data and implemented in the dynamic model.

212 Generally, equations of state (EoSs) are the usual choice for calculation of solubility of a
213 compound (mixture of compounds) in scCO₂. Their application requires knowledge of the critical
214 temperature and pressure of the pure compounds comprising the mixture. It should be noted,
215 however, that in many cases of complex systems, which, for different reasons, have to be
216 represented by a model compound(s), not always the most appropriate one(s) is chosen, because
217 of the lack of information on its (their) critical properties.

218 In our case, the most suitable representative of chia seed oil, following the results of the analyses,
219 is the TAG trilinolenin. Having said that, however, two very important issues should be taken into
220 consideration: *i*) lack of any experimental information on the VLE of trilinolenin+scCO₂; *ii*) total
221 lack of data (both experimental and estimated) on the thermophysical properties of trilinolenin.

222 Hence, though trilinolenin is the most adequate representative of the chia seed oil, the
223 uncertainties that will be intertwined into the solubility predictions via its estimated properties
224 could be so substantial that they might lead to a misrepresentation of the VLE of the binary
225 (trilinolenin+scCO₂), e.g. to an erroneous prediction of the extent of the vapour-liquid region,
226 which, however, could not be identified and verified (see issue *i*).

227 In view of the above, we chose triolein as the TAG to represent the chia seed oil, which was
228 motivated by two reasons: 1) there are experimental data available on the VLE of the binary
229 triolein+scCO₂ and 2) the estimated thermophysical parameters of triolein used by us have been
230 proved to represent in an acceptable way the VLE of the system [33].

231 The solubility (mole fraction) of a compound in the SC fluid may be expressed as:

$$y_i = \frac{x_i \varphi_i^L}{\varphi_i^V} \quad (10)$$

232 where φ_i^L and φ_i^V are the fugacity coefficients of triolein, representing the chia oil in our case, in
233 the liquid and SC fluid phase, respectively.

234 We employ the predictive Soave-Redlich-Kwong (PSRK) cubic EoS [34] to calculate the fugacity
235 coefficients of triolein in the liquid and vapor phases, respectively, and use the values for its
236 critical temperature and pressure reported by Coelho et al. [33].

237

238 **3. Results and Discussion**

239 **3.1 Supercritical CO₂ extraction**

240 The experimental kinetic curves, obtained for the SCE of chia oil from DCS and ECS are
241 displayed on Fig. 1a and 1b, respectively. For DCS, the extraction yield (mass of oil/mass of
242 seeds) increased with pressure and temperature, and was in the range from 13.3 % (at 25 MPa and
243 40 °C) to 18.6 % (at 45 MPa and 60 °C) after 240 min extraction time (Fig. 1a).

244 At the experimental conditions studied in this work, a crossover effect on the overall extraction
245 yield was not observed. Rocha Uribe et al. [19] at operational conditions (27.2-40.8) MPa and
246 (40-60) °C, which are very similar to ours, reported analogous behavior pattern, while Ixtaina et
247 al. [18] observed a crossover point within the same range of pressures (25-45) MPa and
248 temperatures (40-60) °C as those studied by us.

249 Considering the total oil (19.9 % mass) contained in DCS, the recovery values (mass of oil
250 extracted/mass of oil in the seeds) achieved in this work ranged from (66.7 to 93.5) %, and are
251 consonant with the results reported by Ixtaina et al. [17,18] and Scapin et al. [20], who employed
252 high-quality chia seeds containing (32-34) % mass of oil, from different geographical origins, as
253 a raw material.

254 Fig. 1b shows the CO₂ flow rate effect on the oil yield when ECS are used. Pressure and
255 temperature were set at 45 MPa and 40 °C, respectively. The reasons behind choosing these
256 particular experimental conditions were that they proved to be the optimal ones for obtaining
257 higher oil recoveries and ALA concentrations from DCS (see section 3.2).

258 As shown (Fig. 1b), extraction curves overlap at the end of the extraction process, and hence
259 similar oil extraction yields (24.6-25.2) % were achieved independently of the CO₂ flow rate
260 applied. Taking into consideration that the initial oil content for ECS was 28.3% mass, and that
261 the recoveries obtained were between (86.9-89.9) %, it can be concluded that practically all

262 available oil was extracted after the extraction time (240 min). Nevertheless, during the early
263 stages of the extraction, when the free oil located on the surface of the seeds is extracted and the
264 mass transfer resistance is negligible, the extraction rate increased with the CO₂ flow. At that
265 point, the mass of oil extracted at the lowest CO₂ flow rate (0.44 g·min⁻¹) was 1.7-fold higher than
266 the obtained at the highest flow rate (0.76 g·min⁻¹).

267

268 **3.2 Analysis of fatty acid composition**

269 Fig. 2 shows the fatty acid composition of oils from both sets of chia seeds. ALA was the main
270 fatty acid (55.58-67.45%) in the oils, followed by linoleic acid (17.2-23.5%). In respect of DCS
271 (Fig. 2a), the fatty acid profile was very similar for both pressures examined (25 and 45 MPa).
272 With regard to the influence of temperature, the concentration of ALA in the extract was lower at
273 60 °C (n-6/n-3 ratios around 0.26 and 0.42 at 40 and 60 °C, respectively, data not shown).
274 Likewise, the fatty acid profiles obtained from ECS at the different CO₂ flow ratios (Fig. 2b) were
275 very similar (PUFA and ALA concentrations around (81% and 59%, respectively). Our results
276 agree well with those of other authors, who used chia seeds from several geographical origins,
277 and applied different extraction methods and operational conditions [7-11,17-20].

278

279 **3.3 Kinetics modelling results and discussion**

280 The model described in Section 2.5 was solved in gPROMS to simulate the evolution of yield
281 over time for the oil extracted from the two different sets of chia seeds, namely DCS and ECS, at
282 the operational conditions of interest to the experiment.

283 For the ECS, the initial oil content of the matrix, w_{sum} , is 0.283 kg·kg⁻¹ solid, while for DCS
284 $w_{sum,0}$ is 0.199 kg·kg⁻¹ as discussed in Section 2.5.

285 There are four unknown parameters in the model: b , k_f , w_t and K . As the number of experimental
286 data points limits the number of model parameters that can be estimated within a reasonable
287 confidence interval, predefined fixed values should be assigned to some of the above parameters.

288 The value of parameter b , which should be $\gg 1$, was determined after some preliminary
289 calculations and sensitivity analysis of its influence on the extraction kinetics modelling. It was

290 verified that the best value was $b = 40$, and hence it was used in the kinetics model for all cases
291 of DCS and ECS examined.

292 The value of k_f for each case studied was estimated following Coelho et al. [33], who used the
293 relation of Wilke and Chang [35]. The k_f values obtained were then set as constants in the kinetics
294 model, thus reducing the degrees of freedom. For the DCS case, the best values of k_f obtained are
295 displayed in Table 1. For the ECS case, where pressure and temperature remain constant, a single
296 k_f value was used for the three scCO₂ flow rates applied (Table 2).

297 Hence, the maximum content corresponding to monolayer adsorption, w_t , and the partition
298 coefficient K are the two model parameters left to be estimated by fitting the dynamic model to
299 the experimental data.

300 The best estimated values of K and w_t are shown in Table 1 and Table 2, for the DCS and ECS
301 cases, respectively.

302 For DCS, the influence of temperature on the partition coefficient is pronounced – K increases by
303 an order of magnitude with the increase of temperature, while the increase of K values with
304 pressure is not so noticeable (Table 1). This behavior shows that the bond between the solute and
305 the matrix weakens with increasing the temperature of the extraction, which, in its turn, leads to
306 an increase in partition coefficient values, favoring thus the CO₂ phase, while the adsorbent
307 capacity generally decreases.

308 The influence of scCO₂ flow rate on K is demonstrated for the case of SCE of ECS (Table 2). As
309 shown, the values of K decrease with the increase of scCO₂ flow rate.

310 The deviations between the experimentally measured and the calculated yields, expressed by the
311 AARDs (%), are also shown (Table 1 and Table 2, respectively). For the DCS case, there is a
312 good qualitative and quantitative agreement between the simulated and experimental extraction
313 yield curves, as demonstrated on Fig. 1a and Table 1. The only exception being the case at 25
314 MPa and 60 °C where the AARD is higher. The latter was not unexpected taking into
315 consideration the somewhat different trend of the particular experimental extraction curve in
316 comparison to the other three.

317 For the ECS case, the simulated extraction curves follow very well the pattern of the experimental
318 ones and overlap at the end of the extraction. Thus, the kinetics modelling results verify the
319 experimentally observed fact that the oil extraction yields are not influenced by the CO₂ flow rate
320 applied. The AARD values obtained confirm the very good agreement between the experimental
321 and simulated results (Table 2).

322 The evolution of the oil concentration during extraction in the solid matrix inside the extractor
323 and in the exiting fluid stream was simulated. The results for DCS and ECS are presented in Fig.
324 3a and 3b, respectively.

325 As depicted in Fig. 3a, increasing the pressure leads to a faster and more efficient extraction.
326 However, that effect is moderate at 40 °C and at the first stage of the extraction, while it becomes
327 more significant when the operating temperature is set to 60 °C.

328 Fig. 3b shows a positive effect of the increased scCO₂ flow rate on the speed of extraction. Thus,
329 for ECS, on the one hand, the change of oil concentration in the solid phase follows the pattern
330 observed for the DCS (Fig. 1a), and reaches the same final value regardless of the CO₂ flow rate.
331 On the other hand, a higher yield and lower solid phase concentration are being achieved with
332 smaller flowrates.

333 As far as we are aware, these are the first data demonstrating the evolvement of the oil
334 concentration in both the fluid and solid phases during scCO₂ extraction of chia seeds. Taking
335 into consideration that a single model compound is used to represent the oil, the results obtained
336 are quite adequate. Furthermore, they provide valuable information to be used with confidence in
337 a subsequent process design stage.

338

339 **4. Conclusions**

340 This work presents for the first time the results of modelling the experimental kinetics data of
341 SCE of oil from two sets of chia seeds, ECS and DCS. The SCE experiments demonstrated that
342 the highest oil yield (18.6 %) obtained from DCS was achieved at the highest pressure and
343 temperature applied (45 MPa and 60 °C). Furthermore, at these operational conditions practically
344 all the oil was exhausted (93.5 % oil recovery). As can be expected, the extraction yields achieved

345 from ECS, as compared to those from DCS, were higher (24.6-25.2) %, but their values were not
346 influenced by the CO₂ flow rate applied. Nevertheless, the increase in the CO₂-to-chia mass ratio
347 enhanced up to 1.7 times the oil extraction rate at the early stages of extraction. Concentrations
348 of ALA in the range (55-67) % in oils were attained. Furthermore, the oils obtained from both
349 seeds (DCS and ECS) presented a similar fatty acid profile.

350 The kinetics modelling was performed applying a new approach, which intertwines the complex
351 interaction between kinetics and solubility. For the purpose of modelling, triolein was chosen as
352 chia seeds oil representative compound. The model equations were solved in gPROMS
353 ModelBuilder environment, and parameter estimation was performed to obtain some model
354 parameters.

355 The results obtained demonstrate that albeit the simplifications introduced in the model, there is
356 a good agreement between the calculated and experimental extraction yields at the SCE operating
357 conditions examined.

358 Finally, the valuable information on the mass transfer of the extraction process of ECS and DCS
359 obtained can serve as a solid basis for the development of industrial applications targeting the
360 valorization and monetarization of chia seeds and in particular of the highly underused DCS.

361

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434

435 **FIGURE CAPTIONS**

436 **Fig. 1** Experimental (symbols) and simulated (lines) cumulative extraction curves obtained for
437 (a) DCS (40 g·min⁻¹ CO₂ flow rate), and (b) ECS (45 MPa and 40 °C)

438

439 **Fig. 2** Fatty acid composition (% of total fatty acids) of oils extracted from (a) DCS (40 g·min⁻¹
440 CO₂ flow rate) and (b) ECS (45 MPa and 40 °C). Extraction time: 240 min

441

442 **Fig. 3** Simulated profile of oil concentration in the solid (chia seeds, large picture) and fluid
443 (scCO₂, small picture) phases during extraction for (a) DCS (40 g·min⁻¹ CO₂ flow rate), and (b)
444 ECS (45 MPa and 40 °C)

445

446

447

(a)

(b)

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Table 1 Estimated values of K and w_t , and mass transfer coefficients (k_f) for triolein, at different experimental conditions and constant CO_2 flow rate ($40 \text{ g}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$) from DCS. The AARDs represent the deviations between the experimental and calculated yield values

P (MPa)	T ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	K ($\text{kg plant}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}\text{ CO}_2$)	k_f (min^{-1})	w_t ($\text{kg}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}\text{ CO}_2$)	AARD (%)
25	40	3.22E-3	1.51E-5	8.04E-2	4.82
25	60	1.36E-2	3.08E-5	8.04 E-2	9.49
45	40	4.27E-3	7.03E-4	5.76 E-2	5.64
45	60	2.47E-2	4.58E-4	5.20 E-2	2.13

Table 2 Estimated values of K and w_t for triolein at 45 MPa and 40 °C, and varying scCO₂ flow rate for ECS. Triolein mass transfer coefficients $k_f = 7.03\text{E-}4$. The AARDs represent deviations between the experimental and calculated yield values

F (kg·min ⁻¹)	K (kg plant·kg ⁻¹ CO ₂)	w_t (kg·kg ⁻¹ CO ₂)	AARD (%)
27	2.00E-2	6.01E-2	1.22
40	1.69E-2	8.25E-2	2.47
54	9.28E-3	8.07E-2	6.65